

Towards automated prediction of metabolites and non-substrates of cytochrome P450 2D6 and 3A4 enzymes by protein-ligand docking

Sascha Herzinger¹, Michael C. Hutter*²

¹ Luxembourg Centre For Systems Biomedicine
University of Luxembourg
6, Avenue du Swing
L-4367 Belvaux
Luxembourg

² Center for Bioinformatics
Saarland University
Campus Building E2.1
D-66123 Saarbruecken
Germany
Tel: ++49 681 30270703
Fax: ++49 681 30270702
E-mail: michael.hutter@bioinformatik.uni-saarland.de

Abstract:*Background:*

CYP2D6 and CYP3A4 are two major enzymes that contribute to the metabolic conversion of xenobiotics. Therefore it is of interest to predict the sites of metabolism in pharmaceutical compounds.

Methods:

Molecular docking was carried out applying AutoDock4.2 to generate a large number of docking poses for 95 ligands comprising substrates as well as non-substrates within structural models of these cytochromes. The obtained conformations were analyzed in a semi-automated way to assign potential hydroxylations, *N*- and *O*-dealkylations, as well as oxidation of sulfur, nitrogen, and C=C double bonds. The distance between the iron atom of the cytochrome and the ligand atom found closest in conjunction with the kind of that atom was used to assign potential sites of metabolism. Furthermore, we applied the Wilcoxon-Mann-Whitney test to investigate whether identical distributions of ligand conformations could be obtained by performing substantially fewer docking runs.

Results:

We found that the vast majority of all docking poses within a range of 3 kcal/mol of the best ranked conformation contain the experimentally observed sites of reactions. On the other hand, also most non-productive conformations are found within this range. The number of required docking runs to obtain highly similar distributions of ligand poses compared to 1000 runs increases drastically with the number of flexible side chains that are included.

Conclusions:

The unambiguous classification into substrates and non-substrates solely based on the distribution of the type of binding modes is not feasible. Likewise, the amount of false positive matched sites suggests to use docking in combination with ligand-based prediction methods.

Key Terms:

Cytochrome P450 – A superfamily of enzymes that are ubiquitously found in all species due to their role in biosynthesis.

docking pose – Conformation of the ligand in the binding pocket of its supposed receptor as produced by a computational algorithm, usually of iterative nature, and subject to varying initial conditions.

HEM group – The enzymatic activity of Cytochrome P450 is mediated by a porphyrin and the associated iron, which can undergo changes in its oxidation state and its coordination sphere, giving rise to a catalytic redox cycle.

RMSD – The root mean square deviation given in Ångström is a measure of the difference between two sets of Cartesian coordinates, for example two conformations of the same molecule.

site of metabolism – The atom or chemical group in a molecule that is subject to a specific biochemical modification by a metabolic enzyme.

Abbreviations:

CYP, cytochrome P450

HEM, prosthetic heme (haem) group

MD, molecular dynamics

MM, molecular mechanical

QM, quantum mechanical

RMSD, root mean square deviation

SOM, site of metabolism

Introduction

Cytochrome P450 enzymes (CYPs) are abundantly involved in the metabolic conversion of pharmaceutically relevant compounds, which makes them important target. Estimates range from 80 to over 90% of all marketed drugs, whereby the isoenzymes 3A4, 3A5, 2D6, 2C9, 2C19, and 1A2 contribute most.¹⁻³ During preclinical development further CYPs are screened in experimental assays, such as 4A11, 2E1, 2C8, 2C18, 2B6, 2A9, 1B1 (mainly active in the liver), as well as 1A1 (lung). For this purpose, the recombinant human isoenzymes are usually expressed in *E. coli*.⁴ Among other enzymes, such as Flavin-containing monooxygenase, Alcohol dehydrogenase, Aldehyde dehydrogenase, Monoamine oxidase and several peroxidases that contribute to the so-called phase I reactions, Cytochrome P450 enzymes mediate predominately oxidation by the formal insertion of oxygen into C-H bonds, but a series of other modifications have been experimentally observed.⁵ These comprise *N*-, *O*-, and *S*-dealkylation, hydrolysis, epoxidation, *S*- and *N*-oxidation, aldehyde and alcohol oxidation, desulfuration, dehalogenation, reduction of nitro groups, cyclization, and decyclization. Of course these reactions are not limited to pharmaceutical substances as they also affect natural substrates and katabolites.

It is easy to see that the experimental determination of corresponding drug metabolites is laborious. Therefore substantial effort has been undertaken in order to theoretically predict such sites of metabolism (SOM).⁶ Most difficult is the prediction of regioselective reaction products, whereas classification approaches that indicate whether a substance is likely to be a substrate, inhibitor, or inducer is beneficial in virtual screening as well. The later task is, however, still difficult because inhibitors may be metabolized to some extent. Likewise, compounds can be substrates of multiple CYPs. In particular CYP3A4 is known as being rather unselective, due to its large binding pocket. Furthermore, genetic variations of CYPs, best known for CYP2D6, may render some isoforms dysfunctional and thus complicate prediction.³ Thus, theoretical methods typically refer to the wild-type CYP isoforms, due to the availability of experimental data, for example the review of Rendić that covers an extensive collection of substrates, inhibitors, and inducers of nine CYPs.⁵ A further publicly available source was published by Breneman et al.⁷

Depending whether molecular information about the ligand is used only, or whether additional structural aspects of the respective CYPs are included, two categories of prediction models arise. In any case, such information must be defined as a set of variables derived from the ligand and, if included, from the CYP. Doing so allows to apply well established machine learning algorithms, such as decision trees, *k*-nearest neighbor, naïve Bayes, neural networks,

or support vector machines.⁶ In their study Carbon-Mangels and Hutter noted two results: First, the prediction accuracy was better for more specific CYPs, i.e. CYP2D6 than for the much more promiscuous CYP3A4. Second, the simple naïve Bayes method performed better on unbalanced data sets (substantially more substances in one class than in the other class) than support vector machines.⁸ Including structural information about the respective CYP is generally assumed to improve the prediction accuracy. Corresponding descriptors comprise for example molecular interactions fields or catalyticophores.^{9,10} Computed reaction probabilities can furthermore be used to rank potential metabolites as done in the SyGMA approach for metabolic conversions of both Phase I and Phase II.¹¹

Taking physico-chemical considerations into account, the distribution of metabolic products is dependent on several aspects in general: First, is the corresponding site of the ligand close enough to the reactive species of the HEM group? Second, is such a reactive pose likely to be adopted or are other orientations inside the binding pocket more likely? And finally, is the reaction possible at all with respect to the energetic barrier? The latter question can be answered using the results of quantum chemical calculations on suitable model systems. Different levels of molecular orbital theory were used for this purpose in MetaSite, CypScore, SMARTCyp, and the NAT approach.^{9,12-15} The catalytic mechanism that takes place in CYPs has been investigated in detail by Thiel et al. using QM/MM-approaches.¹⁶ The distribution of binding poses over time could be obtained by molecular dynamics (MD) simulations in principle, but the doing so is prohibitive regarding the actual time scale, which ranges from micro seconds to milli seconds. However, MD can be applied to equilibrate poses generated by preceding docking runs.^{17,18} An alternative way to include protein flexibility (in particular rotations of amino acid side chains in the active center) upon docking is to use multiple pre-computed conformations of the enzyme.¹⁹⁻²²

Previously, docking has been used frequently to generate energetically favorable poses of substrates in CYPs.⁶ However, the routine application for in silico screening requires the automated evaluation of obtained poses and their interpretation. Due to the extensive computational demand of docking it is also of interest to limit the number of docking runs for each compound to a reasonable minimum. Here, we applied AutoDock to generate a large number of docking poses within the active sites of CYP2D6 and CYP3A4 including flexible side chains to obtain a comprehensive distribution of binding poses. These were subsequently analyzed in a semi-automated way distinguishing between inhibitory and reactive ligand

binding modes. Furthermore, metabolic conversions at potential SOMs are assigned using a simple set of rules.

Methods

Ligand preparation and docking

Three-dimensional structures of all ligands were generated manually and energetically optimized to a gradient norm below $0.1 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1} \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ applying the MM+ force field within Hyperchem.²³ An in-house PERL script was used to compute Gasteiger-Marsili charges and to merge non-polar hydrogens.²⁴ Assignment of rotatable bonds and final preparation for docking was performed with AutoDockTools (Version 1.5.6rc3).²⁵ Structural models for CYP2D6 and CYP3A4 were created on the basis of the corresponding X-ray crystallographic data (pdb entry codes 3TBG and 1TQN,²⁶ respectively) in order to include the entire binding pocket in the grid box, and to account for flexible side chains (see Table 1). The selection of flexible residues was based on the comparison of various X-ray structures with bound ligands, where these side chains in the active center showed pronounced conformational variability for different inhibitors. Water, other solvent molecules, ions, and ligands were removed. For the protein part AMBER charges were computed by AutoDockTools, whereas for the HEM group Gasteiger-Marsili charges were applied. To the HEM iron a partial charge of $+0.400 e$ was assigned manually, which corresponds to the value in the AMBER force field obtained by restrained electrostatic potential fit for the Fe(II) state. The partial charges of the ligating nitrogen atoms in the HEM group were therefore adjusted by subtracting $-0.1 e$, respectively. This is in line with previous docking studies on other human CYPs.²⁷ A total of 1000 docking runs (poses) for each ligand with 2,500,000 maximum energy evaluations (medium setting) during the Lamarckian genetic algorithm were generated using AutoDock (Version 4.2), otherwise default settings were applied.²⁵

Docking results were then evaluated in a semi-automated way, making use of in-house PYTHON and PERL scripts. In contrast to the build-in clustering of AutoDock, which assigns poses according to the RMSD of the whole ligand, here we assigned reoccurring poses based on the distance between the HEM iron and the respective ligand atom that is considered as potentially reactive site. For this purpose a distance criterion of 4.5 \AA as upper boundary was chosen. If atoms next to certain experimentally determined SOMs appear closest to the iron, these are matched to that site as follows:

Assignment of atoms and potential reactions

It is known that *N*- and *O*-dealkylation can proceed via formal hydroxylation of their adjacent carbon atoms as well as direct oxidation of the heteroatom itself.²⁸ Therefore, aliphatic carbons next to a nitrogen are assigned to the latter atom, because *N*-dealkylation, or the more rare *N*-hydroxylation, is in this case preferred to hydroxylation at that carbon. Similarly, aliphatic carbons next to an oxygen are assigned to the latter, assuming *O*-dealkylation instead of hydroxylation. However, atoms next to nitrogens susceptible to *N*-oxidations, carbons next to C=C double bond oxidations or *S*-oxidations, as well as aliphatic carbons next to aliphatic hydroxylation sites are not assigned to the respective SOM. For aliphatic hydroxylation only sp^3 hybridized carbon atoms are considered.

Classification of ligands on the basis of experimental data

Substances for which no metabolic products for the respective CYP isoenzyme have been reported in the literature used for this study^{5,29-31} are referred to as “non-substrates”. Conversely, all other ligands are termed “substrates” even if they exhibit some inhibitory functionality. To avoid bias regarding count of compounds and substrate specificity we used the same set of 95 ligands, which cover medical drugs and drug-like substances, for both CYP2D6 and CYP3A4. The list of compounds and number of metabolites for each ligand is provided as appendix.

The flowchart of SOM assignment, docking, and subsequent analysis is shown in Figure 1. For the statistical comparison of the obtained docking poses, the Wilcoxon-Mann-Whitney test ($p < 0.05$) was used as implemented in the *R* program package, applying default parameters.³² Docking distributions taken from the first *n* runs were compared to those obtained from the total of 1000 docking runs for each ligand.

Results and Discussion

X-ray structures of CYP inhibitors typically show a coordinative binding of a nitrogen by its lone electron pair as sixth ligand of the HEM iron, for example the nitrogen of the imidazol moiety of ketoconazole in CYP3A4 (pdb entry code 2V0M).³³ The corresponding structure contains even two ligand molecules, which is due to the larger binding pocket of CYP3A4 compared to other CYPs, and the large excess concentration of the inhibitor during crystallization. On the other hand, during the catalytic mechanism the substrate must be in close contact to the reactive iron species (referred to as compound I, or as Cpd I) comprising a radical cation FeO fragment. In both cases iron is formally positively charged and the ligand is bound in the direct vicinity. Thus we modeled the HEM group without an oxygen atom to

allow the distinction of inhibitory binding modes from those that are potentially reactive on the basis of the chemical nature of ligand atoms being in close contact to the iron. The corresponding inhibitory (non-active) binding mode of ritonavir in CYP3A4 is present in the X-ray structure (pdb entry code 3NXU),³⁴ whereas also metabolic conversions occur (hydroxylation, *N*-demethylation, and further bond cleavages at nitrogen atoms).⁵

To include the structural mobility of the enzymes, particularly upon ligand binding, we treated residues within the binding pocket that possess large side chains as flexible during docking (see Table 1). For CYP2D6, Hritz and co-workers observed considerable rearrangements of the side chains of Phe120, Glu216, and Phe483, whereas Asp301 was somewhat translated.²⁰ These movements influenced the binding mode of ligands in the pocket. All of these residues were treated flexible, here. From the superposition of several X-ray crystallographic structures of CYP3A4 with bound inhibitors we identified a total of seven active site residues that showed substantial conformational changes and were thus included in the flexible part (see Table 1). For both CYP2D6 and CYP3A4 we observed that the residues possessing larger side chains (phenylalanine and arginine) also showed stronger displacements (computed as RMSD, see Table 1) compared to the smaller amino acids. We attribute this to the molecular rearrangement upon binding ligands of different shape.

In contrast to most other studies on the prediction of SOMs, we also investigated a substantial number of non-substrates including inhibitors of CYP2D6 and of CYP3A4 (see Table 2 and appendix). This should allow to recognize the most frequent false positive SOMs as obtained by docking, and furthermore to identify criteria that enable a superior distinction between actual substrates and non-substrates of the respective CYP in conjunction with the future use of ligand-based prediction method.

Our previous docking studies involving the human CYP11B2 as well as CYPs from other species, showed that the best-ranked pose was usually not indicating the main metabolite, and was less often adopted than the second-ranked or third-ranked pose, respectively.^{27,35} On the other hand, the experimental product distribution was reflected in a semi-quantitative way, taking lower-ranked poses into account. This is in line with the findings of Danielson et al. for the bioactive poses in CYP2C9.²² We attribute this observation to the nature of the scoring function of AutoDock that was optimized for inhibitors and not for substrates.²⁵ To take these limitations of the scoring function into account, and in turn to reduce the number of unlikely high energy ligand conformations and quasi random poses, we chose an upper margin of 3 kcal/mol from the best binding mode.

Our docking results show that from all actual SOMs more than 95% are retrieved for the substrates of CYP2D6 and 97% for those of the CYP3A4 substrates, considering all docking poses obtained. Of those poses that are within 3 kcal mol⁻¹ of the respective lowest energy conformation, on average 88% for CYP2D6 and 97% for CYP3A4 contain the corresponding bioactive poses. However, the majority of all found binding poses is also found within that energy range (96% for CYP2D6 and 88% of CYP3A4), which gives rise to a large number of false positive SOM predictions based on this energy criterion. Conversely, 19% (CYP2D6) and 16% (CYP3A4) of the non-productive binding poses of all compounds are also found within this range that accounts for states that are accessible by the energy arising from the degrees of freedom and the thermal energy at room temperature. Non-substrates of CYP2D6 contain 26% (average) non-active binding modes within this range, whereas this value is only 14% for the substrates. The trend is reversed for CYP3A4: 21% of inhibitory binding modes for the substrates and 16% for the inhibitors. We suggest that is caused by the higher specificity of CYP2D6 in comparison to CYP3A4, which is known to possess a larger binding pocket and to metabolize a broader range of substances. Therefore, a clear distinction between substrates and non-substrates based on the kind of binding mode or its distribution is not feasible. Vasanthanathan et al. reported a similar outcome of their docking studies on CYP1A2.³⁶ Binding positions and thus matching of SOMs were found in good agreement with experimental data, whereas classification of ligands into actives (substrates) and inactives turned out to be more difficult, even when applying machine learning. Corresponding descriptors should provide more detailed information about the chemical environment of the atom that is found close to the HEM iron with respect to its reactivity and accessibility. Published approaches have used empirically derived sets of reactivity rules based on the SMIRKS notation,¹¹ or various parameters obtained from quantum chemical calculations, whereby estimation of the hydrogen atom abstraction energy is the most frequently being used.⁶ Further descriptors that influence chemical reactivity are, e.g. bond orders, atomic charges, and the local electron density, which can be derived from the molecular wave function.

Whereas we collected the results of each single docking run of AutoDock to assign corresponding clusters that represent the binding poses, Danielson et al. used AutoDockVina that clusters only those binding modes that are within a similar energy range of the lowest energy conformation found.²² This gives rise to a top-*n* sequence of binding modes, whereby they found 96% of the bioactive conformations within the top-3 position for substrates of CYP2C9 including protein flexibility.

We also analyzed how often a certain docking pose was found, which is reflected by its corresponding cluster size. For both CYP2D6 and CYP3A4 on average 88% of all clusters contain more than 2% of the total number of docking runs (20 out of 1000 runs) for each compound. Likewise, only few matched SOMs are found in smaller clusters.

To test whether similar distributions of docking poses are adopted if less than 1000 docking runs are carried out, we compared the corresponding distributions obtained from the first n runs, for $n = 50, 100, 250, 500,$ and 750 , applying the Wilcoxon-Mann-Whitney test. The fractions of statistically identical distributions ($p < 0.05$) for the investigated 95 ligands are given in Table 3. For CYP2D6 (6 flexible residues) highly similar distributions were obtained with 500 runs, whereby 94.7% of all can be considered as being identical. For CYP3A4, which has 7 flexible residues in our model, however, much more runs (>700) are necessary to achieve similar distributions. Compared to the CYP2D6 model, the flexible amino acids also show more pronounced movements (RMSD values are given in Table 1), thus giving rise to substantially more possible ligand conformations.

Assignment of SOMs solely by the distance to the HEM iron certainly leads to an abundance of false positives. We used an upper boundary of 4.5 Å to limit such cases to a certain extent. Other docking studies that also included the HEM moiety without having an oxygen as sixth ligand of the iron applied 5.0 Å or even 6.0 Å.^{20,22,37} Additional criteria, such as inclusion of the atomic accessible surface area were used as measures of appropriate orientation of SOMs towards the HEM iron for specific reactions.²¹

We observed that atoms carrying a negative partial charge (nitrogen, oxygen, fluorine, and chlorine) are frequently found close to the HEM iron, which carries a positive partial charge. This can be attributed to the electrostatic term in the scoring function of AutoDock, which is dominant. Inhibitory binding of ligands in X-ray crystallographic structures, however, occurs via lone pair interactions, for example ketoconazole and ritonavir as mentioned above. While binding modes involving halogens and carbonyl oxygens can easily be ruled out as SOMs, the situation for nitrogen is more complicated. *N*-dealkylation is likely in aliphatic vicinity, whereas *N*-oxidation may occur in aromatic six-membered rings. Corresponding rules were included in our assignment of potentially reactive versus non-productive binding modes (see Method section for details).

The labeling of inactive atoms, potential, and actual SOMs in the compounds from the literature data turned out to be the most time-consuming task requiring human interaction. Clearly, this step can be automated having a corresponding database at hand.

Regarding potential SOMs, we found that aromatic hydroxylations show high rates of false positives (normalized to the number of corresponding atoms being present in the respective ligands) for both CYP2D6 (11.9) and CYP3A4 (17.8). Such cyclic structures are very often present as side chains in molecules and therefore easily accessible. We observed that many falsely predicted aromatic hydroxylations are in ortho position to other substituents (halogens, methoxy, and methyl groups). Such modifications are rare (e.g. nefadozone) and application of corresponding heuristic rules could therefore reduce the number of such wrongly predicted SOMs. Conversely, aromatic hydroxylation is experimentally found often in para position to hetero atoms. Whereas the false positive rate for aliphatic hydroxylation (10.5) is similar to that of aromatic hydroxylation in CYP2D6, the corresponding rate (7.4) in CYP3A4 is considerably lower. Even lower is the false positive rate for *N*-dealkylation (4.7) in CYP3A4. Due to the low amount of other reactions in both CYPs, no meaningful rates or trends can be derived.

The extensive comparison of regioselective prediction methods for CYP isoenzymes by Zaretski et al. shows that the accuracy of assigning *O*- and *N*-dealkylation benefits most of such approaches for a larger set of substrates.⁷ Conversely, the number of true positive hydroxylation sites is diminished in favor of fewer false positives compared to our assignment using only docking results. Nevertheless, it transpires that is not possible to reliably assign SOMs solely on the basis of docking poses and their distribution. In this context it would be of interest to investigate the performance of knowledge-based predictions approaches for data sets comprising a substantial number of non-substrates. The accuracy of machine learning methods usually improves when information of the respective other compound class is included in the training set.

Future Perspective and Executive Summary

* Docking using flexible side chains yields the ligand poses responsible for nearly all actual SOMs within 3 kcal mol⁻¹ of the lowest energy conformation.

* To obtain a highly similar distribution of ligand poses as for 1000 docking runs, the number of runs should not be less than 500 for CYP2D6 (6 flexible residues), and not less than 750 for CYP3A4 (7 flexible residues).

* Distinction between substrates and non-substrates solely on the basis of the distribution of active vs. non-active docking poses and their distributions is not feasible.

* We suggest that docking results can be applied as filter to identify those sites that are accessible by the respective CYP prior to the use of algorithms that contain knowledge-based or quantum chemical information on model substrates.

Financial & competing interests disclosure

The authors have no relevant affiliations or financial involvement with any organization or entity with a financial interest in or financial conflict with the subject matter or materials discussed in the manuscript. This includes employment, consultancies, honoraria, stock ownership or options, expert testimony, grants or patents received or pending, or royalties.

No writing assistance was utilized in the production of this manuscript.

References

- (1) Rendic, S.; Guengerich, F. P. Survey of Human Oxidoreductases and Cytochrome P450 Enzymes Involved in the Metabolism of Xenobiotic and Natural Chemicals. *Chem. Res. Toxicol.* **2015**, *28*, 39-42.
- (2) Guengerich, F. P. Cytochrome P450s and Other Enzymes in Drug Metabolism and Toxicity. *AAPS J.* **2005**, *8*, E101-E111.
- (3) Lewis, D. F. V. Human P450s in the Metabolism of Drugs: Molecular Modelling of Enzyme-Substrate Interactions. *Expert Opin. Drug. Metab. Toxicol.* **2005**, *1*, 5-8.
- (4) Schroer, K.; Kittelmann, M.; Lütz, S. Recombinant Human Cytochrome P450 Monooxygenases for Drug Metabolite Synthesis. *Biotech. Bioengin.* **2010**, *106*, 699-706.
- (5) Rendic, S. Summary of Information on Human CYP Enzymes: Human P450 Metabolism Data. *Drug Metabol. Rev.* **2002**, *34*, 83-448.
- (6) Kirchmair, J.; Williamson, M. J.; Tyzack, J. D.; Tan, L.; Bond, P. J.; Bender, A.; Glen, R. C. Computational Prediction of Metabolism: Sites, Products, SAR, P450 Enzyme Dynamics, and Mechanisms. *J. Chem. Inf. Model.* **2012**, *52*, 617-648.
- (7) Zaretski, J.; Rydberg, P.; Bergeron, C.; Bennett, K. P.; Olsen, L.; Breneman, C. M. RS-Predictor Model Augmented with SMARTCyp Reactivities: Robust Metabolic Regioselectivity Predictions for Nine CYP Isoenzymes. *J. Chem. Inf. Model.* **2012**, *52*, 1637-1659.
- (8) Carbon-Mangels, M.; Hutter, M. C. Selecting Relevant Descriptors for Classification by Bayesian Estimates: A Comparison with Decision Trees and Support Vector Machines Approaches for Disparate Data Sets. *Mol. Inf.* **2011**, *30*, 885-895.
- (9) Cruciani, G.; Carosati, E.; De Boeck, B.; Ethirajulu, K.; Mackie, C.; Howe, T.; Vianello, R. MetaSite: Understanding Metabolism in Human Cytochromes from the Perspective of the Chemist. *J. Med. Chem.* **2005**, *48*, 6970-6979.
- (10) Oh, W. S.; Kim, D. N.; Jung, J.; Cho, K.-H.; No, K. T. New Combined Model for the Prediction of Regioselectivity in Cytochrome P450/3A4 Mediated Metabolism. *J. Chem. Inf. Model.* **2008**, *48*, 591-601.

- (11) Ridder, L.; Wagener, M. SyGMa: Combining Expert Knowledge and Empirical Scoring in the Prediction of Metabolites. *ChemMedChem* **2008**, *3*, 821-832.
- (12) Olsen, L.; Rydberg, P.; Rod, T. H.; Ryde, U. Prediction of Activation Energies for Hydrogen Abstraction by Cytochrome P450. *J. Med. Chem.* **2006**, *49*, 6489-6499.
- (13) Hennemann, M.; Friedl, A.; Lobell, M.; Keldenich, J.; Hillisch, A.; Clark, T.; Göller, A. H. CypScore: Quantitative Prediction of Reactivity towards Cytochromes P450 Based on Semiempirical Molecular Orbital Theory. *ChemMedChem* **2009**, *4*, 657-669.
- (14) Rydberg, P.; Gloriam, D. E.; Zaretski, J.; Breneman, C.; Olsen, L. SMARTCyp: A 2D Method for Prediction of Cytochrome P450-Mediated Drug Metabolism. *ACS Med. Chem. Lett.* **2010**, *1*, 96-100.
- (15) Liu, R.; Liu, J.; Tawa, G.; Wallqvist, A. 2D SMARTCyp Reactivity-Based Set of Metabolism Prediction for Major Drug-Metabolizing Cytochrome P450 Enzymes. *J. Chem. Inf. Model.* **2012**, *52*, 1698-1712.
- (16) Shaik, S.; Cohen, S.; Wang, Y.; Chen, H.; Kumar, D.; Thiel, W. P450 Enzymes: Their Structure, Reactivity, and Selectivity-Modeled by QM/MM Calculations. *Chem. Rev.* **2010**, *110*, 949-1017.
- (17) Kuhn, B.; Jacobsen, W.; Christians, U.; Benet, L. Z.; Kollman, P. A. Metabolism of Sirolimus and Its Derivative Everolimus by Cytochrome P450 3A4: Insights from Docking, Molecular Dynamics, and Quantum Chemical Calculations. *J. Med. Chem.* **2001**, *44*, 2027-2034.
- (18) Park, J.-Y.; Harris, D. Construction and Assessment of Models of CYP2E1: Predictions of Metabolism from Docking, Molecular Dynamics, and Density Functional Theoretical Calculations. *J. Med. Chem.* **2003**, *46*, 1645-1660.
- (19) Lill, M. A.; Dobler, M.; Vedani, A. Prediction of Small-Molecule Binding to Cytochrome P450 3A4: Flexible Docking Combined with Multidimensional QSAR. *ChemMedChem* **2006**, *1*, 73-81.
- (20) Hritz, J.; de Ruiter, A.; Oostenbrink, C. Impact of Plasticity and Flexibility on Docking Results for Cytochrome P450 2D6: A Combined Approach of Molecular Dynamics and Ligand Docking. *J. Med. Chem.* **2008**, *51*, 7469-7477.
- (21) Moors, S. L. C.; Vos, A. M.; Cummings, M. D.; Van Vlijmen, H.; Ceulemans, A. Structure-Based Site of Metabolism Prediction for Cytochrome P450 2D6. *J. Med. Chem.* **2011**, *54*, 6098-6105.
- (22) Danielson, M. L.; Desai, P. V.; Mohutsky, M. A.; Wrighton, S. A.; Lill, M. A. Potentially Increasing the Metabolic Stability of Drug Candidates via Computational Site of Metabolism Prediction by CYP2C9: The Utility of Incorporating Protein Flexibility via an Ensemble of Structures. *Eur. J. Med. Chem.* **2011**, *46*, 3953-3963.
- (23) *HYPERCHEM*; Version 6.02, Hypercube Inc.: Gainsville, FL 1999.
- (24) Gasteiger, J.; Marsili, M. Iterative Partial Equalization of Orbital Electronegativity-Rapid Access to Atomic Charges. *Tetrahedron* **1980**, *36*, 3219-3288.
- (25) Morris, G. M.; Huey, R.; Lindstrom, W.; Sanner, M. F.; Belew, R. K.; Goodsell, D. S.; Olson, A. J. Autodock4 and AutoDockTools4; Automated Docking With Selective Receptor Flexibility. *J. Comput. Chem.* **2009**, *30*, 2785-2791.
- (26) Yano, J. K.; Wester, M. R.; Schoch, G. A.; Griffin, K. J.; Sout, C. D.; Johnson, E. F. The Structure of Human Microsomal Cytochrome P450 3A4 Determined by X-Ray Crystallography to 2.05-Å Resolution. *J. Biol. Chem.* **2004**, *279*, 38091-38094.
- (27) Hobler, A.; Kagawa, N.; Hutter, M. C.; Wudy, S. A.; Hannemann, F.; Bernhardt, R. Human Aldosterone Synthase: Recombinant expression in *E. coli* and Purification Enables a Detailed biochemical Analysis of the Protein on the Molecular Level. *J. Steroid Biochem. Mol. Biol.* **2012**, *132*, 57-65.
- (28) Meunier, B.; de Visser, S. P.; Shaik, S. Mechanism of Oxidation Reactions Catalyzed by Cytochrome P450 Enzymes. *Chem. Rev.* **2004**, *104*, 3947-3980.

- (29) Rochat, B.; Amey, M.; Gillet, M.; Meyer, U. A.; Baumann, P. Identification of Three Cytochrome P450 Isoenzymes Involved in *N*-Demethylation of Citalopram Enantiomers in Human Liver Microsomes. *Pharmacogenetics* **1997**, *7*, 1-10.
- (30) Nakajima, M.; Nakamura, S.; Tokudome, S.; Shimada, N.; Yamazaki, H.; Yokoi, T. Azelastine *N*-demethylation by Cytochrome P-450 (CYP)3A4, 2D6, and CYP1A2 in Human Liver Microsomes: Evaluation of Approach to Predict the Contribution of Multiple CYPs. *Drug Metab. Dispos.* **1999**, *27*, 1381-1391.
- (31) Stiborová, M.; Poljaková, J.; Martínková, E.; Ulrichová, J.; Simánek, V.; Dvorák, Z.; Freu, E. Ellipticine Oxidation and DNA Adduct Formation in Human Hepatocytes is Catalyzed by Human Cytochromes P450 and Enhanced by Cytochrome *b5*. *Toxicology* **2012**, *320*, 233-241.
- (32) R Development Core Team. *R*; version 2.3.1 , R Development Core Team 2006. <http://cran.r-project.org> (accessed Jan 7, 2006)
- (33) Ekroos, M.; Sjogren, T. Structural Basis for Ligand Promiscuity in Cytochrome P450 3A4. *Proc. Natl. Acad. U.S.A.* **2006**, *103*, 13682-13687.
- (34) Sevrioukova, I. F.; Poulos, T. L. Structure and Mechanism of the Complex between Cytochrome P4503A4 and Ritonavir. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* **2010**, *107*, 18422-18427.
- (35) Khatri, Y.; Girhard, M.; Romankiewicz, A.; Ringle, M.; Hannemann, F.; Urlacher, V. B.; Hutter, M. C.; Bernhardt, R. Regioselective Hydroxylation of Norisoprenoids by CYP109D1 from *Sorangium cellulosum* So ce56. *Appl. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* **2010**, *88*, 485-495.
- (36) Vasanathan, P.; Hritz, J.; Taboureau, O.; Olsen, L.; Jørgensen, F. S.; Vermeulen, N. P. E.; Oostenbrink, C. Virtual Screening and Prediction of Site of Metabolism for Cytochrome P450 1A2 Ligands. *J. Chem. Inf. Model.* **2009**, *49*, 43-52.
- (37) de Graaf, C.; Oostenbrink, C.; Keizers, P. H.; van der Wijst, T.; Jongejan, A.; Vermeulen, N. P. E. Catalytic Site Prediction and Virtual Screening of Cytochrome P450 2D6 Substrates by Consideration of Water and Rescoring in Automated Docking. *J. Med. Chem.* **2006**, *49*, 2417-2430.

Table 1. Details of the structural models used during docking with AutoDock.

enzyme	PDB entry	flexible residues	average RMSD of residue^a	grid box dimensions and resolution^b	grid box center^c
CYP2D6	3TBG	Phe120	2.040	58 · 62 · 62 0.375 Å	18.215 52.725 -6.948
		Glu216	2.150		
		Asp301	1.523		
		Ser304	0.878		
		Thr309	0.190		
		Phe483	2.621		
		Arg106	4.366		
		Phe108	2.435		
CYP3A4	1TQN	Leu211	1.514	58 · 63 · 63 0.375 Å	-22.659 -21.586 -12.408
		Arg212	2.608		
		Phe215	1.983		
		Phe304	1.726		
		Arg372	3.047		

^a The given root mean square deviation (in Å) is given for the side chain atoms of the respective residue as average of all docking poses of the 95 docked ligands.

^b points in x, y, and z direction, as well as spacing

^c x, y, and z coordinates within the corresponding X-ray structure

Table 2. Summary of docking results.

quantity	CYP2D6	CYP3A4
number of substrates	51	69
number of non-substrates	44	26
total number of SOMs	82	133
SOMs directly matched (%)	79.3	91.0
SOMs matches incl. neighboring atoms (%)	95.1	97.0
SOMs not found (%)	4.9	3.0
number of <i>N</i> -dealkylations/matched	7/6	33/31
number of <i>O</i> -dealkylations/matched	7/6	5/5
number of <i>N</i> -oxidations/matched	2/1	10/9
number of <i>S</i> -oxidations/matched	5/5	5/5
number of C=C-oxidations/matched	0/0	1/1
number of aliphatic hydroxylations/matched	20/20	39/38
number of aromatic hydroxylations/matched	27/26	28/28

Table 3. Influence of the number of docking runs on the distribution of ligand poses. Reported are the fractions of statistically identical distributions compared to those obtained for 1000 dockings (Wilcoxon-Mann-Whitney test, $p < 0.05$)

system	Number of docking runs						
	50	100	150	250	500	750	1000
CYP2D6	0.042	0.137	0.189	0.305	0.947	1.000	1.000
CYP3A4	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	0.032	0.333	0.989	1.000

Figure 1. Flowchart of the procedure pursued in this study.

Appendix

List of compounds that were used for docking and number of considered metabolites for CYP2D6 and CYP3A4. Experimental data were collected from following references:

1. Rendić S. Summary of Information on Human CYP Enzymes: Human P450 Metabolism Data. *Drug Metabol. Rev.* 34, 83-448 (2002).
2. Rochat B, Amey M, Gillet M, Meyer UA, Baumann P. Identification of Three Cytochrome P450 Isoenzymes Involved in *N*-Demethylation of Citalopram Enantiomers in Human Liver Microsomes. *Pharmacogenetics* 7, 1-10 (1997).
3. Nakajima M, Nakamura S, Tokudome S, Shimada N, Yamazaki H, Yokoi T. Azelastine *N*-demethylation by Cytochrome P-450 (CYP)3A4, 2D6, and CYP1A2 in Human Liver Microsomes: Evaluation of Approach to Predict the Contribution of Multiple CYPs. *Drug Metab. Dispos.* 27, 1381-1391 (1999).
4. Stiborová M, Poljaková J, Martínková E, Ulrichová J, Simánek V, Dvůrák Z, Freu E. Ellipticine Oxidation and DNA Adduct Formation in Human Hepatocytes is Catalyzed by Human Cytochromes P450 and Enhanced by Cytochrome *b5*. *Toxicology* 320, 233-241 (2012).

Table A1. List of compounds used in this study and corresponding number of metabolites.

Substances without metabolites were considered as non-substrates.

compound	2D6	3A4
alfentanil	0	2
alprenolol	2	0
aminopyrine	1	1
amitriptyline	3	1
amlodipine	0	1
antipyrine	0	1
aprindine	1	0
azelastine	1	1
barnidipine	0	4
bergamottin	0	0
betaxolol	0	0
bufuralol	1	0
caffeine	0	1
celecoxib	0	1
chlorpromazine	1	1
cinnarizine	1	0
cisapride	0	3
citalopram	1	1

clemastine	0	0
clozapine	1	3
codeine	1	1
cortisol	0	1
debrisoquin	7	0
delavirdine	1	2
dexamethasone	0	1
dextromethorphan	2	1
diazepam	0	2
diclofenac	0	1
diltiazem	1	1
DMP777	0	2
(<i>E</i>)-doxepin	1	1
doxorubicin	0	0
DPPE (tesmilifene)	2	2
efavirenz	0	1
ellipticine	2	3
felodipine	0	1
fexofenadine	0	0
<i>R</i> -fluoxetine	1	1
fluphenazine	1	0
fluvastatin	1	1
haloperidol	1	1
imipramine	3	2
indinavir	1	4
ketoconazole	0	0
lansoprazole	0	2
lomustine	0	0
loratadine	1	1
losartan	0	0
mequitazine	2	0
mianserin	2	2
mibefradil	0	2
midazolam	0	2
<i>S</i> -mirtazapine	1	2
naringin	0	0
nefazodone	0	3
nevirapine	2	3
nortriptyline	0	1
olanzapine	1	0
<i>S</i> -omeprazole	2	4
paracetamol	1	3
paroxetine	1	0
perazine	0	1
perphenazine	2	1
pimobendan	0	1
pimozide	0	1
pindolol	0	0
praziquantel	0	0
progesterone	3	4
<i>S</i> -propranolol	3	0

quetiapine	1	3
quinidine	0	2
risperidone	1	1
ritonavir	1	3
roquinimex	0	6
salbutamol	0	0
saquinavir	4	7
selegiline	1	1
serotonin	0	0
sertindole	1	1
sertraline	1	1
sildenafil	1	1
tamoxifen	2	2
terbinafine	0	1
terfenadine	3	2
testosterone	0	4
thioridazine	2	0
(+)-tolterodine	1	1
triprolidine	0	0
venlafaxine	1	1
verapamil	0	1
<i>R</i> -warfarin	0	3
zafirlukast	0	0
ziprasidone	0	2
zolpidem	2	4
zotepine	1	3